

COMPARATIVE STUDIES REGARDING WILD PLANTS RESOURCES FROM MOUNTAIN REGIONS, FOR THEIR SUSTAINABLE USE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MOUNTAIN PRODUCTS THAT HIGHLIGHTS THEIR ADDED VALUE

Violeta TURCUȘ^{1,3}, Paul ALBU^{1,3}, Viviane Beatrice BOTA^{1,2}

¹ Centre of Mountain Economy “CE-MONT”, Național Institute for Mountain Biotehhnology, Petreni, nr. 49, 725700, Vatra Dornei, Jud. Suceava, România

² Doctoral School of Biology, Faculty of Biology “Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, BV. Carol I, nr. 11, Iași, Romania

³ Institutul Național de Cercetări Economice “Costin C. Kirițescu” al Academiei Române/ Centrul de Economie Montană (CE-MONT)

Abstract

In this paper, we present the importance of some wild flora taxons and their role in the traditional culture of mountain regions populations. Inhabitants of the Carpathian Mountains still keep knowledge about the harvest and use of wild food and medicinal plants. The region offers important resources for ethnobotanical and gastronomic studies but they are underexplored. We selected from bibliographic sources available in international databases the wild food plants used by Romanians and ethnic minorities from Romania. In the specialized bibliography are mentioned 60 species from 33 families, from which 17 species are common with those used by Romanians. The biggest number of species are harvested by Hungarians (over 200 species). We observed that species of the Rosaceae Family are most commonly used for their fruits. From the majority of species are harvested the aerial vegetative organs and reproductive organs, for preparation of alcoholic beverages, fermented products, jams, sweets, and other conserved forms, followed by prepared dishes like soups, stews, and lastly, their consumption in a fresh state. Exceptionally, the wood is used to smoke meats, and the sap is used to obtain beverages with therapeutic effects. During the Covid-19 pandemic, the consumption has raised for some species with nutritional and medicinal values, with a role in treating respiratory system ailments, and in strengthening the immune system, especially in rural areas and those in which the medical system was overloaded. These studies help in gaining a better understanding of local perceptions, offer important information for development projects and sustainable use of local biodiversity. Some plants that are used in uncommon ways deserve more in-depth studies, showing potential for the gastronomic and medicinal fields, in obtaining some specific mountain products.

Keywords: *food plants, wild flora, Carpathian Mountains, Romania.*

INTRODUCTION

Europe represents an area of increasing interest for ethnobotanical and ethnogastronomy studies, especially mountain regions and that of the Carpathian Mountains, where knowledge about wild plants and their traditional uses are still kept. Studies made until now present mostly data from other European countries (Łuczaj *et al.*, 2012; Carvalho *et al.*, 2010; Tardio *et al.*, 2006), in Romania were performed only a few studies about other residing ethnic minorities (Mattalia *et al.*, 2020; Pawera *et al.*, 2017; Dénes *et al.*, 2012), and sometimes a comparison was made with species used by Romanians (Pieroni *et al.*, 2015). The use of wild flora varies in time and space depending on multiple factors from which the most important is the socio-economic one (Stryamets *et al.*, 2015; Łuczaj *et al.*, 2012). There have been

observed different directions of evolutions often taking place in parallel. On one side is the gradual disappearance of knowledge about the traditional use of wild flora resources, on the other side is the emergence of new trends in modern societies that associate these resources with a healthy lifestyle and they're reintroducing them in various forms of consumption (Łuczaj *et al.*, 2012). The revitalization of traditional practices related to medicinal and edible wild plants is considered important for development plans that aim for the sustainable valorization of local biodiversity. At the same time, they contribute to the preservation of bio-cultural legacy, threatened in the present context, especially in the mountain regions (Pieroni and Sõukand, 2017; Mustafa *et al.*, 2015). These types of studies can sometimes highlight unusual or abandoned practices, of interest for food businesses and the pharmaceutical field. Our purpose for this study was to evaluate the species from wild flora used by Romanians for food purposes, particularly in the mountain regions, considering the possibility of their introduction in sustainable use-pathways, and the development of mountain products with added value.

METHODOLOGY

For this study, we consulted bibliographic resources available on international databases (Web of Science, Springerlink), using key terms (plants, mountain, product, food, uses, Romania, Europe). Out of 2,128 results, only 15 were relevant for our theme, and only 5 included data regarding Romania. We centralized the data related to wild food species used by Romanians and ethnic minorities living in Romania, performing a comparative analysis regarding their share in each community. Species uses exclusively for medicinal purposes were excluded. Moreover, we noted the European trends in search for possible ways to introduce these species in mountain products with added value. The specie's names were verified and actualized according to EURO+MED Database.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Data regarding the wild species collected by Romanians and ethnic minorities from Romania for food purposes are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Wild food species gathered by Romanians and ethnic minorities from Romania

Scientific name (Family)	Common name	Part used	Uses						References
				RO	HU	UK	HT	TA	
<i>Abies alba</i> Mill. (Pinaceae)	Silver fir	Buds, cones, leaves	Alcoholic beverages (distilling buds and cones)		+				Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Acer spp.</i> (<i>A. campestre</i> , <i>A. pseudoplatanus</i>) (Sapindales)	Maple	Fruits, sap, roots	Beverages, young fruits as snacks		+		+		Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012; Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020
<i>Allium ursinum</i> L. (Amaryllidaceae)	Ramson, wild garlic	Aerial parts	Soups, stews; after the leaves turn yellow the bulb is used		++	+			Vári <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012

Scientific name (Family)	Common name	Part used	Uses						References
				RO	HU	UK	HT	TA	
			like onion, for seasoning, as snack						
<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i> L. (Amaranthaceae)	Redroot pigweed	Leaves	Soups, pies	+	+				Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Arctium lappa</i> L. (Compositae)	Greater burdock	Roots	Various dishes		+				Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Armoracia rusticana</i> O. Gaertn. (Brassicaceae)	Horseradish	Root, leaves, whole plant	Salads, seasoning, fresh or fermented, pickles	+	+	+	+	+	Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Artemisia absinthium</i> L. (Compositae)	Wormwood	Aerial parts	Alcoholic beverages		+				Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Atriplex hortensis</i> L. (Chenopodiaceae)	Mountain spinach	Aerial parts	Soups, sarma, pies	+			+	+	Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015
<i>Betula pendula</i> Roth (Betulaceae)	Birch	Sap	Fresh beverage, fermented for wine and vinegar		+	+			Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Carum carvi</i> L. (Apiaceae)	Caraway	Aerial parts, seeds	Seasoning, fermented products, pickles		+	+	+		Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Chenopodium album</i> L. (Chenopodiaceae)	White goosefoot, Fat-hen	Aerial parts	Soups, stews (with cream), seasoning (dry state)		+	+	+		Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Coriandrum sativum</i> L. (Apiaceae)	Coriander	Seeds	Smocking and seasoning meats				+		Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020
<i>Cornus mas</i> L. (Cornaceae)	Cornelian cherry, dogwood	Leaves	Snack		++	+			Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Coryllus avellana</i> L. (Corylaceae)	Hazelnut	Fruits	Jams, fresh state		++	+	+		Vári <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Crataegus monogyna</i> Jacq. (Rosaceae)	Common hawthorn	Fruits, leaves	Fresh state	+	+				Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Fagus sylvatica</i> L. (Fagaceae)	Beech	Wood, fruits, leaves, seeds, sap	Smocking meats; snack; seed oil; leaves eaten fresh		+	+	+		Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Reynoutria japonica</i> Houtt. (sinonim <i>Fallopia japonica</i> Ronse Decr.) (Polygonaceae)	Japanese knotweed	Leaves	Sarma			+			Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015

Scientific name (Family)	Common name	Part used	Uses						References
				RO	HU	UK	HT	TA	
<i>Fragaria vesca</i> L. (Rosaceae)	Woodland strawberry	Fruits	Fresh or frozen, jams, compotes, sweets, juice, syrup		+	+	+	+	Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Gentiana</i> spp. (<i>G. lutea</i> L., <i>G. asclepiadea</i> L.) (Gentianaceae)	Great yellow gentian, willow gentian	Aerial parts	Infusing alcoholic beverages		+		+		Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Helianthus tuberosus</i> L. (Heliantheae)	Jerusalem artichoke	Tubers, flowers	Fresh, pickles; the nectar eaten fresh		+	+			Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Hippophae rhamnoides</i> L. (Eleagnaceae)	Sea buckthorn	Fruits	Jams, fruits conserved in honey, syrup		++				Vári <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Humulus lupulus</i> L. (Cannabaceae)	Common hop	Aerial parts, fruits, flowers	Fresh stems in soups or fried; flowers used for beer or yeast starter		++		+		Vári <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Juglans regia</i> L. (Juglandaceae)	Persian walnut	Fruits, sap	Fresh state, desserts, jams, syrup, alcoholic beverages	+	+			+	Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Juniperus communis</i> L. (Cupressaceae)	Juniper	Fruits	Alcoholic beverages, seasoning, meat marinades and smocking		+				Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Levisticum officinale</i> W. D. J. (Apiaceae)	Lovage	Leaves	Seasoning, pickles	+					Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015
<i>Lilium candidum</i> L. (Liliaceae)	Lily	Flowers	Alcoholic beverages (macerated in brandy)	+					Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015
<i>Malva sylvestris</i> L. (Malvaceae)	Common mallow	Fruits	Alcoholic beverages, vinegar, fresh state, compotes, desserts, seasoning	+	+	+		+	Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Origanum vulgare</i> L. (Lamiaceae)	Oregano	Aerial parts	Seasoning		+		+		Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Oxalis</i> spp. (<i>O. acetosella</i> L., <i>O. stricta</i> L.) (Oxalidaceae)	Sorrel	Leaves, flowers	Salads, seasoning, vinegar		+	+	+		Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012

Scientific name (Family)	Common name	Part used	Uses						References
				RO	HU	UK	HT	TA	
<i>Padus padus</i> L. subsp. <i>padus</i> (sin. <i>P. avium</i> Mill.) (Rosaceae)	Bird cherry	Fruits	Jams, alcoholic beverages		++				Vári <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Papaver rhoeas</i> L. (Papaveraceae)	Poppy	Flowers, Seeds	Desserts, pastry products, petals can be eaten fresh		+		+	+	Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Picea abies</i> L. (Pinaceae)	Norway spruce	Buds, wood	Jams, meat smocking, syrup, alcoholic beverages		+	+	+		Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Pinus</i> sp. (<i>P. sylvestris</i> L., <i>P. nigra</i> Arnold <i>Picea alba</i> Link) (Pinaceae)	Pine	Aerial parts, buds, cones	Siróp		++				Vári <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Polypodium vulgare</i> L. (Polypodiaceae)	Common polypody	Rhizome	Snack		+	+			Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Populus tremula</i> L. (Salicaceae)	Quaking aspen	Wood	Smocking meats				+		Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020
<i>Prunus cerasifera</i> Ehrh. (Rosaceae)	Cherry plum	Fruits, sap	Compote, green fruits used in soups, bortsch (sour agent)	+	+			+	Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Prunus spinosa</i> L. (Rosaceae)	Blackthorn	Fruits	Alcoholic beverages (wine, liqueur); snack		++	+			Vári <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Pyrus communis</i> subsp. <i>pyraster</i> (L.) Ehrh (sin. <i>P. pyraster</i> Burgsd.) (Rosaceae)	Wild pear	Fruits	Alcoholic beverages (liqueur), vinegar, soups with dried fruits		++			+	Vári <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Quercus</i> spp. (<i>Q. robur</i> L., <i>Q. rubra</i> L., <i>Q. cerris</i> L.; <i>Q. pubescens</i> Willd.) (Fagaceae)	Oak	Leaves, young branches, fruits	Leaves added in pickles; fruits eaten boiled, ground for flour; brown beer made of <i>Q. cerris</i> fruits		+	+	+		Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Ficaria verna</i> Huds. (sin. <i>Ranunculus ficaria</i> L.) (Ranunculaceae)	Lesser celandine	Aerial parts	Soups, salads, stews, fresh		++	+			Vári <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Ribes nigrum</i> L. (Grossulariaceae)	Blackcurrant	Fruits	Jams, alcoholic beverages		++				Vári <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i> L. (Fabaceae)	Black locust	Flowers, leaves	Flowers and nectar eaten fresh, flowers fried in pancake	+	+	+		+	Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012

Scientific name (Family)	Common name	Part used	Uses						References
				RO	HU	UK	HT	TA	
			batter, added in wine or bread dough; snack						
<i>Rosa canina</i> L. (Rosaceae)	Dog rose	Fruits	Sweets, jams, alcoholic beverages, syrup, vinegar and beverages made out of petals	+	++	+		+	Vári <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Rosa rugosa</i> L., <i>R. centifolia</i> L. (Rosaceae)	Rugosa rose	Flower (petals)	Jams, sweets, syrup		+		+		Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015
<i>Rubus</i> spp. (<i>R. caesius</i> L. <i>Rubus fruticosus</i> L.) (Rosaceae)	Blackberry	Fruits	Jams, sweets, compotes, infusing alcoholic beverages, juice, syrup		++	+	+		Vári <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Rubus idaeus</i> L. (Rosaceae)	Raspberry	Fruits	Jams, sweets, compote, juice, alcoholic beverages, desserts, syrup		++	+	+		Vári <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Rumex acetosa</i> L. (Polygonaceae)	Sorrel	Leaves	Soups, salads, snack, milk inoculation	+	+	+	+	+	Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Rumex alpinus</i> L. (Polygonaceae)	Monk's rhubarb	Leaves	Stews (with cream), sarma, pies, introduced in various dishes	+	+	+	+	+	Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Sambucus nigra</i> L. (Viburnaceae)	European elder	Flowers, fruits	Flower syrup; sweets, juice, alcoholic beverages from fruits, desserts	+	++		+	+	Vári <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Sorbus</i> spp. (<i>S. aucuparia</i>) (Rosaceae)	European mountain ash	Flowers, fruits	Various dishes		++		+		Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Taraxacum sect. taraxacum</i> F. H. Wigg (sin. <i>T. officinale</i>) (Compositae)	Dandelion	Flowers, leaves, roots	Hone and sweets from flowers, salads from leaves, salads and coffee surrogate from roots	+	++	+	+	+	Vári <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Thymus</i> spp. (<i>T. vulgaris</i> L., <i>T. serpyllum</i> L.) (Lamiaceae)	Wild thyme	Aerial parts	Seasoning	+	+	+	+		Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012

Scientific name (Family)	Common name	Part used	Uses						References
				RO	HU	UK	HT	TA	
<i>Tilia cordata</i> Mill. <i>T. tomentosa</i> Moench (Malvaceae)	Linden	Leaves, flowers	Sarma, flowers added in alcoholic beverages (brandy, palinka, wine)	+	+			+	Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Tussilago farfara</i> L. (Compositae)	Coltsfoot	Aerial parts	Stews, sarma, soups, salads, sweetened syrup from flowers		++	+	+		Vári <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Urtica dioica</i> L. (Urticaceae)	Nettle	Aerial parts	Soup, bortsch, borsh, stews, salads, seasoning	+	++	+	+	+	Vári <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Pieroni <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i> L. (Ericaceae)	Bilberry	Aerial parts, fruits	Alcoholic beverages (afinata), conserved in brandy, juice, syrup, compote, jams, sweets, desserts, fresh, dry or frozen, snack		+	+	+		Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Vaccinium vitis-idaea</i> L. (Ericaceae)	Cranberry	Fruits	Jams, sweets, juice, fresh or dry state		+	+	+		Mattalia <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012
<i>Viburnum opulus</i> L. (Viburnaceae)	European cranberry bush	Leaves	Fresh or dry state, jams, syrup		+	+			Łuczaj <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Dénes <i>et al.</i> , 2012

We identified 60 species, from 33 families, used by Romanians and ethnic Hungarians, Ukrainians, Hutsuls, and Tatars living in Romania (Transylvania – 2 articles, Bukovina – 2 articles, Maramureş – 1 article, Dobrogea – 1 article). Most used species belong to the following families Rosaceae (20%), Compositae (7%), Apiaceae and Polygonaceae (5%), Chenopodiaceae, Viburnaceae, Lamiaceae, and Malvaceae (4%). The rest of 22 families are represented by 2%, meaning only one species from each family was mentioned (Figure 1).

This wide range of used wild plants shows the importance of high biodiversity availability for the preservation of associated traditions.

Most of these species are collected for their aerial vegetative organs and reproductive organs, for the production of a wide variety of products: from alcoholic beverages, fermented products, jams, and preserves, to soups, sour broths, stews, and finally, their consumption in a fresh state. Exceptionally, the wood is used to smoke meat (*Fagus sylvatica*, *Juniperus communis*, *Picea abies*, *Populus tremula*), and the sap for preparing beverages with therapeutic

effect (*Acer* spp., *Betula pendula*, *F. sylvatica*, *Juglans regia*, *Prunus cerasifera*). A preference for the fruits of Rosaceae species was also noted by Sõukand *et al.* (2015), who mentions their use in the preparation of products fermented in alcohol, lactic acid, or acetic acid, probably due to their high content of tannins and phenols. Fermented foods and beverages are an important group in traditional gastronomy based on wild flora resources. A study from 2015 by Sõukand *et al.*, including various states from Eastern Europe, mentions 116 taxons from 37 families, from which a wide variety of fermented foods are obtained. Types of fermented products prepared from different wild plant species include alcoholic beverages, pickles, distillates, vinegar, fizzy drinks, supes/broths with lacto-fermented plants, sourdough bread (Sõukand *et al.*, 2015).

Fig. 1. Percentage of species used from each plant family

From the centralized data results that the highest number of species are collected for food purposes by Hungarians (52.35%), followed by Ukrainians (31.21%), Hutsuls (30.21%), Romanians (18.12%), and Tatars (16.11%) (Figure 2).

Romanians use 18 species in common with the other ethnic minorities. All populations taken into study use 8 common species: *Armoracia rusticana*, *Robinia pseudoacacia*, *Rosa canina*, *Rumex acetosa*, *Rumex alpinus*, *Sambucus nigra*, *Taraxacum* sect. *taraxacum*, *Urtica dioica*. A study on Hungarians living in the Carpathian Basin shows that they use over 200 species from 68 families, the majority being consumed in the rest of Europe as well: fruits of species from genus *Rosa*, *Rubus*, *Cornus*, *Ribes*, *Vaccinium*, fruits, and seeds of *Fagus*, *Quercus*, *Corylus*, *Castanea*, *Trapa*, aerial parts of *Rumex*, *Urtica*, *Humulus*, *Chenopodiaceae*, *Ranunculus*, underground parts of *Lathyrus*, *Helianthus*, *Chaerophyllum*, and *Allium*. In the past were consumed especially underground parts of aquatic and semi-aquatic species like *Typha*, *Sagittaria*, *Phragmites*, *Armoracia*, and steppe species – *Crambe*, *Rumex*. Presently,

the Hungarians living in Transylvania still use around 40 species (Dénes *et al.*, 2012). It can be noted the importance of species from genus *Rosa*, *Rumex*, *Taraxacum*, *Armoracia*, and *Urtica* for different European populations.

Fig. 2. Number of wild food species used by Romanians (RO) Hungarians (HU), Ukrainians (UK), Hutsuls (HT), and Tatars (TA) living in Romania

The study regarding the Hutsuls from Northern Romania and Southern Ukraine shows differences in the number and species of wild plants collected, and the way they use them on both sides of the border. In Romania, the knowledge is transmitted mostly vertically, from one generation to another in one family, while in Ukraine there were reported other types of resources as well, mostly from media. This partially explains the high number of taxa (47), used by Hutsuls from Ukraine, the list including alohton species like *Aloe Vera*, *Aronia melanocarpa*, and *Eleagnus rhamnoides*, while the Hutsuls from Romania use specifically only 11 plant species. There has been noted a propensity for hybridization of knowledge, those local/traditional and those introduced from abroad, especially by media (Mattalia *et al.*, 2020).

Differences have been discovered between Romanians and the Tatar community from Romania, with 36 common species out of a total of 77 food and medicinal species. Romanians tend to use the wild flora more for medicinal purposes, while the Tatars include a higher number of food uses (Pieroni *et al.*, 2015).

The importance of wild flora during the COVID-19 Pandemic

In the rural communities and those in the urban diaspora, the primary response during the pandemic was based on using medicinal plants and on a diet with wild food plants, known to be used for the treatment of respiratory illnesses, strengthening the immune system,

associated with “healthy foods” or functional foods (with nutritional and medicinal values). This type of response was stronger in areas where the health system was overloaded (Pieroni *et al.*, 2020).

In Romania, according to Pieroni *et al.* (2020), the consumption raised for species like wild thyme (*Thymus serpyllum* L.), mint (*Mentha pulegium* L.), fir (*Abies alba* Mill.), and pine buds (*Pinus* spp.), taken as a tea, syrups, extracts, mixed with honey or propolis tinctures, sea buckthorn (*Elaeagnus rhamnoides* (L.) A. Nelson), taken with honey in the morning; garlic (*Allium sativum* L.), onion (*Allium cepa* L.), parsley (*Petroselinum crispum* (Mill.) Fuss), nettle (*Urtica dioica* L.), White Goosefoot (*Chenopodium album* L.), sorrel (*Rumex acetosa* L.), and ramsoms (*Allium ursinum* L.). These are consumed in their fresh state, in salads, soups, fresh and smoothies, or as tea. This study has once more signaled the introduction of alohton species in the human diet, popularized in media for healthy diets and healthy lifestyles (Pieroni *et al.*, 2020).

New trends in Europe regarding the use of the wild flora resources

At an European level, in parallel with the gradual loss of knowledge and traditions related to wild flora, there's an increasing interest in these resources from the part of some intellectuals and gastronomic elites in search of new stimuli, culinary experiences, and healthy diets. We assist to a phenomenon of reintroduction of wild plants in human diets and rediscovery of some traditions, both local and of other cultures. The interest is expressed by a growing number of books, blogs, field guides, workshops, and seminars, new culinary trends, and even the development of a database (Plants for a Future). Wild food plants are more often introduced in the menus of agro-touristic boardinghouses and restaurants (rustic and avant-garde kitchens) that offer a “local experience”, given that the plants used are local, and depending on the season (Fontefrancesco and Pieroni, 2020; Kalle and Sökand, 2016; Łuczaj *et al.*, 2012). Dishes examples: nettle soup, wild fruits dishes (Poland); wild herb teas – *Jasonia glutinosa*, *Sideritis hyssopifolia*, ice-cream infused with *J. glutinosa* served in restaurants in Spain; *S. hyssopifolia* liqueur, patxaran – a beverage from *Prunus spinosa* fruits, with cinnamon, coffee seeds, and sugar in anise liqueur (Navarre), *Centaurea cyanus* fizzy lemonade. Examples of species introduced in the menu of top restaurants, in traditional or reinterpreted dishes: *U. dioica*, *Tamus communis*, *Rorippa nasturtium-aquaticum*, *Montia fontana*, *Allium ampeloprasum*, *Asparagus acutifolius*, *Scolymus hispanicus* (Łuczaj *et al.*, 2012).

On the European market, often in profile stores, are already available a variety of products with wild food species: acorn or *Chicorium intybus* coffee (chicory is also added in industrial cereal coffee), *Allium ursinum* products, birch sap, *Juniperus communis*, and *Taraxacum* spp. syrups, pasta with *Urtica* spp. powder, *Vaccinium myrtillus*, *Cantharellus cibarius*, *J. communis* beer, *Scolymus hispanicus* –gourmet product; house bread baked on *Acorus calamus* leaves (promoted in the “Slow Food” movement, as an added value to a bakery product, highlighting the region's identity as it is a traditional product from NE Poland, Lithuania, Belarus), *Rubus caesius* jams, *H. rhamnoides* juice, products with *Angelica archangelica* stem, *Prunus spinosa* liqueur (Łuczaj *et al.*, 2012; Schunko and Vogl, 2010). Forest mushrooms that before were gathered and conserved only for household consumption, now find their place on store shelves as special products, that respect traditional recipes (mushrooms conserved as pickles, in brine or oil), or are sold fresh in markets next to forest fruits, tea herbs, sometimes *Rumex acetosa* leaves and *Armoracia rusticana* roots (Łuczaj *et al.*, 2012).

Some of these studies reveal new information for the European ethnobotany, like the consumption of *Impatiens parviflora* seeds, *Sambucus nigra* green flower buds, *Ajuga reptans* nectar (Pawera *et al.*, 2017), as well as some unusual uses. In Albania, wild pears were used to prepare vinegar, unripe wild apples as yeast starter, and some unripe wild fruits, birch cambium, and *Sedum album* leaves for initiating yogurt cultures (Pieroni and Sökand, 2017).

CONCLUSIONS

The ethnobotanical studies performed in the region of the Carpathian Mountains regarding the use of wild food plants by Romanians and ethnic minorities from Romania show that they use around 60 wild flora species belonging to 33 families. Most often are collected species from Rosaceae, Compositae, Apiaceae, and Polygonaceae families. Over 50 wild food species are used by Hungarians from Romania, followed by Ukrainian and Hutsuls, with 31 species and 30 species, respectively. Romanians use in common with other ethnic minorities 18 wild species, and only 8 species are commonly used by all populations taken into study. Data shows that species belonging to *Rosa*, *Rumex*, *Taraxacum*, *Armoracia*, and *Urtica* genus hold special importance for European populations, given that they were mentioned in almost all consulted resources. Fermentation is an essential process in traditional gastronomy, being used to obtain a wide variety of products, some already available on the European market. It was noted the emergence of new trends in modern society, that associate the use of wild flora resources with a healthy lifestyle and they reintroduce them in various forms of consumption. The phenomenon takes place in parallel with the disappearance of knowledge about their traditional use in some areas. Species for which are mentioned unusual uses deserve more in-depth studies, as they hold potential for gastronomic and medicinal fields, for obtaining specific mountain products.

Ethnobotanical and ethno-gastronomy studies contribute to a better understanding of local perceptions and offer important data for development projects and sustainable valorization of local biodiversity. At the level of Romanian communities, there is little data regarding the species collected from wild flora and their uses, highlighting the need for more ethnobotanical studies.

REFERENCES

- Carvalho AM, Morales R.** 2010. Persistence of wild food and wild medicinal plant knowledge in a northeastern region of Portugal. In: Pardo-de-Santayana M, Pieroni A, Puri RK, editors. *Ethnobotany in the New Europe: people, health, and wild plant resources*. New York NY: Berghahn Books, p 147–171.
- Dénes A, Papp N, Babai D, Czúcz B, Molnár Z.** 2012. Wild plants used for food by Hungarian ethnic groups living in the Carpathian Basin. *Acta Societatis Botanicorum Poloniae*, 81(4): 381–396. <https://doi.org/10.5586/asbp.2012.040>.
- Euro+Med.** 2006. Euro+Med PlantBase – the information resource for Euro-Mediterranean plant diversity. Published on the Internet <http://ww2.bgbm.org/EuroPlusMed/> [1.09.2020].
- Fontefrancesco MF, Pieroni A.** 2020. Renegotiating situativity: Transformations of local herbal knowledge in a Western Alpine valley during the past 40 years. *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*, 16(1):1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13002-020-00402-3>.

- Kalle R, Sõukand R.** 2016. Current and Remembered Past Uses of Wild Food Plants in Saaremaa, Estonia: Changes in the Context of Unlearning Debt. *Economic Botany*, 70(3):235–253. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12231-016-9355-x>.
- Łuczaj Ł, Pieroni A, Tardío J, Pardo-De-Santayana M, Sõukand R, Svanberg I, Kalle R.** 2012. Wild food plant use in 21st century Europe: The disappearance of old traditions and the search for new cuisines involving wild edibles. *Acta Societatis Botanicorum Poloniae*, 81(4):359–370. <https://doi.org/10.5586/asbp.2012.031>.
- Mattalia G, Stryamets N, Pieroni A, Sõukand R.** 2020. Knowledge transmission patterns at the border: Ethnobotany of Hutsuls living in the Carpathian Mountains of Bukovina (SW Ukraine and NE Romania). In *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-24160/v2>.
- Mustafa B, Hajdari A, Pieroni A, Pulaj B, Koro X, Quave CL.** 2015. A cross-cultural comparison of folk plant uses among Albanians, Bosniaks, Gorani and Turks living in south Kosovo. *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*, 11(1):1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13002-015-0023-5>.
- Pawera L, Łuczaj Ł, Pieroni A, Polesny Z.** 2017. Traditional Plant Knowledge in the White Carpathians: Ethnobotany of Wild Food Plants and Crop Wild Relatives in the Czech Republic. *Human Ecology*, 45(5):655–671. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10745-017-9938-x>.
- Pieroni A, Sõukand R.** 2017. The disappearing wild food and medicinal plant knowledge in a few mountain villages of North-Eastern Albania. *Journal of Applied Botany and Food Quality*, 90:58–67. <https://doi.org/10.5073/JABFQ.2017.090.009>.
- Pieroni A, Nedelcheva A, Dogan Y.** 2015. Local knowledge of medicinal plants and wild food plants among Tatars and Romanians in Dobruja (South-East Romania). *Genetic Resources and Crop Evolution*, 62(4):605–620. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10722-014-0185-3>.
- Pieroni A, Vandebroek I, Prakofjewa J, Bussmann RW, Paniagua-Zambrana NY, Maroyi A, Torri L, Zocchi DM, Dam ATK, Khan SM, Ahmad H, Yeandl Y, Huish R, Pardo-de-Santayana M, Mocan A, Hu X, Boscolo O, Sõukand R.** 2020. Taming the pandemic? The importance of homemade plant-based foods and beverages as community responses to COVID-19. *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*, 16(1):1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13002-020-00426-9>.
- Schunko C, Vogl CR.** 2010. Organic farmers use of wild food plants and fungi in a hilly area in Styria (Austria). *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1746-4269-6-17>.
- Sõukand R, Pieroni A, Biró M, Dénes A, Dogan Y, Hajdari A, Kalle R, Reade B, Mustafa B, Nedelcheva A, Quave CL, Łuczaj Ł.** 2015. An ethnobotanical perspective on traditional fermented plant foods and beverages in Eastern Europe. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 170(1):284–296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2015.05.018>.
- Stryamets NN, Elbakidze MM, Ceuterick MM, Angelstam PP, Axelsson RR.** 2015. From economic survival to recreation: Contemporary uses of wild food and medicine in rural Sweden, Ukraine and NW Russia. *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13002-015-0036-0>.
- Tardío J, Pardo-De-Santayana M, Morales R.** 2006. Ethnobotanical review of wild edible plants in Spain. *Botanical Journal of the Linnean Society*, 152(1):27–71. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-8339.2006.00549.x>.